

SILENT NOISE CHANNEL NOISE IN VISUAL COMMUNICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Visual communications are disseminated across channels such as web-based channels, broadcast channels, print channels and others. Visual designers manipulate textual messages, photographs, charts and other graphic devices to create complex interrelating presentations. In doing so, designers become mediators of their clients' messages. Communications theories from various related disciplines have shown that noise occurs within communications channels and can compromise the fidelity of messages. This paper relates various communications models to visual communications scenarios and finds similar occurrences of noise in visual communications design. We explore several subtopics, including visual noise within text, data graphics and visual noise created by interrelated objects within graphic layouts. Visual examples are shown illustrating occurrences of noise within each subtopic. Terminology and concepts are considered to enable visual designers to establish a body of knowledge relating to visual channel noise and to communicate them in a multidisciplinary forum.

Keywords: Channel noise, comprehensibility, message fidelity

INTRODUCTION

One of today's vibrant areas of research involves the use of new technologies to disseminate visually-based messages. From iPhone screens to newspaper redesigns to multi-technology awareness campaigns, visual designers are searching for new ways to make communication more effective. Are we missing critical knowledge in this technology-focused exploration? Are we creating precise messages to send through our communication channels?

Claude Shannon created *Information Theory* in the late 1940's. Researching digital communications systems, he made the curious discovery of communication "noise". Shannon postulated that digital messages could contain noise, and that it entered the system at the point of the system's "signal" (Shannon, Weaver, 1998). (see figure 2)

Shannon's theories focus on digital data transmission systems. Can these theories shed light on visual communication systems? Can visual messages contain visual noise?

WHAT IS VISUAL NOISE?

Visual messages contain code. They contain texts that are codified language, diagrams and charts that are codified information, and images that represent people, places and things. When the message's visual code gets to the message receiver, the receiver decodes the message and reconfigures it into meaning (as this paper is being decoded now). If the code is interfered with – if it does not get to the intended receiver of the message intact – then the meaning of the message is compromised. Visual noise compromises the receiver's ability to see the code they were intended to see, such as in the following example.

IF THE CHANNEL IS WEAKENED, THE MESSAGE IS COMPROMISED.

Figure 1. A textual message may contain visual noise, making the code hard to decipher. Text: Mesquite Medium

This paper compares various existing theories of message fidelity to similar issues in visual communication by looking at communications models in a multidisciplinary way. By interrelating behavioural science, information theory, visual communications theory, typographic design, and statistics, it observes the behaviours of visual design,

text, graphic information, and the interplay between elements on a visual plane.

This paper hypothesizes that visual messages are often compromised – that message fidelity is lost – due to *noise* in visual communications systems (*channels*). It focuses on the elements of a visual message, not the machines that transmit or print messages. These message elements include text, graphics, charts, and images, which are formed into mediated messages by visual designers. It is critical that visual designers understand the effects that their skill levels and choices have on message fidelity.

This paper will begin to assemble previously piecemeal evidence into a fundamental body of knowledge by grouping undesirable visual effects under the concept of channel noise. This knowledge could empower visual designers to make more informed design decisions when mediating messages, and offer terminology that may help various interrelated disciplines understand these phenomena.

METHOD

This paper is a literature review. It reviews parallel theories and applies them to visual communications through a multidisciplinary model. This will allow it to build its perspectives on existing theories based on research in other fields (such as information theory, education etc.). The goal is to use standardized theories that shed light on message fidelity, rather than introducing improvised approaches into the body of visual communication research. The paper then examines research in typography, legibility, comprehensibility, education, statistical communication and visual communication to find evidence of noise within communication channels in these specific areas.

GLOSSARY

The terms listed below have the following definitions within the paper's context.

Noise: disruptions, distortions and inaccuracies within a conveyed message.

Channel: a medium used to convey messages, such as a telephone line, a page or eyesight.

Channel noise: interference in a message sent through a channel, such as background noise in a telephone conversation.

Comprehensibility: the ability of a person to understand a message.

Message fidelity: the ability of a message to remain uncompromised by effects such as noise. **Mediated message:** a message from a sender to a receiver, conveyed by an intermediate agent, such as a designer.

SHANNON AND INFORMATION THEORY

To begin, the manifestation of noise in visual communications channels will be compared with the fundamental ideas of Shannon's *Mathematical Theory of Communication* - his seminal theory of information developed in 1948 - and build parallels based on Shannon's model of a simplistic digital communication system (Shannon, 1948).

Shannon's model (*figure 2*) reads from left to right. The information source (message sender) sends a message, which is given to a message transmitter. The transmitter creates a signal. The *signal* is conveyed over a channel – shown as the signal and *received signal* arrows – to a receiver where the message is finally given to the destination (message receiver). In the diagram below, noise enters Shannon's system in the channel, and is shown as being mechanistic in nature. Shannon's system can be thought of as similar to a telephone system, with a message sender, transmitter, telephone wire, receiver and message recipient. The diagram depicts each step of transmission as being a discreet part of the system (Shannon, 1948).

Figure 2. Shannon's diagrammatical description of a digital communications system (Shannon, 1948: 381)

Warren Weaver's popularizations of Claude Shannon's theories were first published in 1949 in *Scientific American*. Weaver was able to succinctly conceptualize and convey the basic essence of Shannon's ideas (Shannon, Weaver, 1998).

Shannon and Weaver both noted the fact that the transmitter, shown as the second phase of the diagram, must often encode the message.

In telephony this operation consists merely of changing sound pressure into proportional electric current. In telegraphy we have an encoding operation that produces a sequence of dots, dashes and spaces on the channel corresponding to the message. (Shannon, 1948: 381)

It is generally true that when there is noise, the received signal exhibits greater information (Shannon, Weaver, 1998). This suggests that noise combines with the original signal, increasing the amount of information within the signal. It also identifies that there is unwanted information in the received signal. Noise (unwanted information) combines with wanted information. In order to get the transmitted information Weaver suggested that the noise had to then be removed.

Weaver also made it clear that the theory did not describe the conveyance of meaning. The word *information*, in this theory, is used in a special sense that must not be confused with its ordinary usage. In particular, information must not be confused with meaning (Shannon, Weaver, 1998: 8).

Like Weaver, we must note that we are not studying the meaning that is visually conveyed, but the purity of the visual channel that is used. Channel noise is what makes code hard to see, while the code itself may or may not be hard to understand. As in *figure 1*, the words are easy to understand, but the letters are hard to visually discern. Seeing the letters is the visual channel. Understanding them is the visual code.

Shannon believed his theories might have other applications. Commenting on his own research, Shannon stated, “these results suggest that under certain conditions the human being, in manipulating information, may adopt codes and methods akin to those in information theory” (Guizzo, 2003: 56). Weaver stated, “practically everything said applies equally well to music of any sort, and still to moving pictures, as in television.” (Shannon, Weaver, 1998: 1)

Weinberger also suggests that other disciplines may consider Shannon’s model.

Shannon’s theory defines information at its most abstract: not the dots and dashes of the telegraph or the modulations of radio waves or the pixels on your LCD, but information abstracted from any instance of its communication. Because of this utter abstractness, information theory can be applied to everything, from traffic to clouds. (Weinberger, 2008)

We feel Shannon’s theories may contribute to a better understanding of the behaviour of mediated messages.

FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS OF SHANNON’S MODEL

Wilbur Schramm is considered the first to modify Shannon’s model of communication. Schramm introduced a new model with the concept of feedback in what he termed as “message loops” (Bowman, Targowski, 1987: 26). This model assumes the communication is between 2 people, and is not linear as Shannon’s model shows, but cyclical. Schramm’s sender and receiver alternate as the cyclical feedback between them occurs as shown in *figure 3*.

Figure 3. Schramm’s modification of Shannon’s model, 1954. Retrieved May 15, 2011 from <http://communicationtheory.org>

Schramm developed the model shown in *figure 4* (on the following page) through the influences of Charles Osgood’s concepts describing the impacts of social context and shared fields of experience on the meaning of conveyed messages. The model also replaces the transmitter and receiver of Shannon’s model with an encoder and decoder. Schramm considered the source and encoder to be one person, and the decoder and destination to be another (Bowman, Targowski, 1987: 25). This model describes communications between 2 people, as in the model above (*figure 3*).

Figure 4. The Osgood-Schramm communication model, 1954. (Crilly, 2008: 431)

Osgood and Schramm's models do not delineate noise as Shannon's model does. Osgood and Schramm's Field of Experience relates more to understanding the code of a message than it relates to being able to see the code itself. Channel noise is therefore not considered in this model.

Bowman and Targowski (1987: 26) state that from this point forward, virtually every communication model has included the concepts of social context and feedback. For this reason, most subsequent communications models are less relevant to the issues of visual channel noise.

Osgood and Schramm's models move communication theory forward, but relate less to visual communication systems. Visual communication behaves more like Shannon's linear process (although sign language, semaphore and Twitter may be exceptions). It is arguable that a magazine or website offers a feedback loop, but the feedback is greatly delayed and does not behave as a conversational feedback loop.

The consumer (*of a visual message*) must then interpret the product without direct access to the designer or their intentions, and therefore negotiated clarifications of meaning are not possible (Crilly, 2008: 429). Feedback loops for most mediated messages are a series of linear messages, which are due, in part, to the time it takes to prepare complex visual statements.

OTHER VIEWS ON INFORMATION THEORY

In his 1993 paper, *Comprehensibility*, Petterson simplifies the original perspective of Shannon, stripping away the equipment to focus on sender>message>receiver relationship.

Communications takes place when a sender wants to convey one or more messages to one or more receivers. The sender transfers the messages to the receivers with the help of different media. A medium and its contents (the message) constitute a 'representation' (Petterson, 1993: 2).

Figure 5: Petterson's basic communications system (Petterson, 1993: 2). (redrawn)

According to Petterson (1993: 2), communication may not always function. When message fidelity is compromised, the sender may fail to reach the receiver. Petterson's focus is on the codes and content of communication messages, not the channels through which it moves, but he identifies the potential of a disrupted message.

In *A Synthetic Model of Mass Persuasion* (1976: 13), Kneupper and Underwood state, "Noise includes all mechanistic and humanistic considerations and general technological barriers and limitations". This perspective suggests humanistic factors may also create noise. They develop this further, stating "As source encoders, communications skills affect communication in two ways; first, they affect ability to analyze self-purpose and intentions; second, they affect ability to encode messages which are intended" (Kneupper, Underwood, 1976: 13). Firstly, they feel the designer's personal intentions may augment the original meaning of a message. Secondly, they feel the designer's skill set may not be adequate to convey accurate messages.

These ideas may be related to Petterson's diagram of a system of comprehensibility, as communications skills for encoding may include, for example, the legibility of a designer's chosen typeface. In relation to comprehensibility, Petterson states that a message relies on readability, legibility and content value, but also on credibility and aesthetics, the sender's writing methods and the receiver's ability to read the message (Petterson, 1993: 4).

Encoded messages are distributed through channels, which Kneupper and Underwood relate directly to the senses, defining them as "seeing, hearing, touching, smelling and tasting" (Kneupper, Underwood, 1976: 12-13). In a purely visual communications model the main channel is essentially "seeing".

For the purposes of this paper we will draw a visual communication diagram (figure 6). A cube represents the information source's raw message. The message receiver is a person. The mediated message is the image on the plane, reflecting the visual communication channel. This message, according to Shannon and Weaver (1998), and Kneupper and Underwood (1976), contains noise. This diagram focuses on the behaviour of the mediated message, its accurate representation of the source, and the noise it may contain.

How do elements like text, graphics and images generate noise when being seen? Are mediators generating channel noise themselves?

Figure 6. Visual communications diagram

To understand the behaviour of channel noise in visual communications we will focus on three specific components of visual messages: text, data graphics, and layouts of interactive visual elements.

CHANNEL NOISE WITHIN TEXT

David Ogilvy, founder of the Advertising Agency, Ogilvy and Mather, started his working life as a statistical researcher. One of the byproducts of being a researcher was that he began to research his own advertising effectiveness, often on huge national campaigns. Ogilvy began to see patterns between advertising success rates and ad design through decades of advertising research. Here are several of his insights:

The eye is a creature of habit. People are accustomed to reading books, magazines and newspapers in lower case.

Which typefaces are easiest to read? Those which people are accustomed to reading, like the

Century family, Caslon, Baskerville and Jenson. The more outlandish the typeface, the harder it is to read. The drama belongs in what you say, not in the typeface.

Yet another common mistake is to set copy in a measure which is too wide or too narrow to be legible. People are accustomed to reading newspapers which are about 40 characters wide. (Ogilvy, 1983: 96)

These observations suggest that Ogilvy had discovered that something was affecting the comprehensibility of his work. His messages were not received if text was not in lower case, familiar typefaces or within appropriate margins for legibility, (Wheildon, 1995). This paper refers to these phenomena as visual channel noise.

COMPREHENDING TEXT

In the 1980s, Colin Wheildon conducted a research project to test some of Ogilvy's observations. His study carried out in the suburbs of Sydney Australia over a 9-year period (1982-1990), began with 300 participants that totaled 224 by its completion (Wheildon, 1995).

Wheildon's resulting book, *Type & Layout, how typography and design can get your message across-or get in the way* (1995), uncovers many aspects of visual "channel noise". Wheildon experimented with text size, colour, boldness, headline styles, body text styles, basic design layouts and type design.

Wheildon was searching for levels of comprehensibility. Comprehensibility is often confused with legibility – the ability to see and distinguish letterforms (such as in the study of highway signage effectiveness). Comprehensibility refers to the ability of written messages to be understood, such as in continuous texts in books (Wheildon, 1995). His method was to get participants to read samples of articles of interest, typeset in different ways, and test them with questionnaires exposing their retention of key information. The following are some of the findings of Wheildon's study that correspond to visual channel noise.

Wheildon found that continuous texts should be black. He found that coloured text, especially when reproduced in bright or muted colours had very low comprehension levels – about one-seventh that of

black text. Printing black text on heavy background images, or on shades of black was also found to create visual noise, especially on shades greater than 10 percent black. Wheildon found white text on black backgrounds to be impossible to comprehend. Bold text used for narrative texts was found to be less than half as comprehensible as regular text weights (Wheildon, 1995: 97-101).

Figure 7. Various colours of text and shades of backgrounds

Wheildon’s findings showed that bodies of text must never be set aligning on the right and ragged left (*flush right*). This setting was almost one seventh as comprehensible as text aligning left and right (justified text). Justified text was almost twice as comprehensible as text set aligned left and ragged right (*flush left*) (Wheildon, 1995: 110).

Figure 8. Various alignments of bodies of text, from left to right: *flush right*, *justified*, and *flush left*.

Another finding was that bodies of continuous text should be set in serif type. Wheildon found that serif texts were about five times as comprehensible as sans serif texts (Wheildon, 1995: 59).

In research collated by the British Medical Council in 1926, it was asserted that the absence of serifs in sans serif body type permitted what the council referred to as irradiation, an optical effect in which space between lines of type intruded into the letters, setting up a form of light vibration, which militated against comfortable reading. Serifs, the research said, prevented this irradiation. Thus serif types were easier to read. Magazine editors and art directors argue that sans serif body type is clean, uncluttered and attractive. And so it is. (Wheildon, 1995: 56)

Wheildon’s reference to the British Medical Council’s 1926 findings describes an early observation of visual channel noise, perceived by a group of communicators who demanded message fidelity.

LETTERFORMS AND TYPE DESIGN

Understanding how we read can shed light on how visual noise can be reduced. Understanding basic type attributes can add further perspective.

People don’t read single letters – they read letter groupings. Our brains have trained themselves to see the distinct letter shapes within a word, yet read the word (Larson, 2004). The brain is familiar with these letter shapes and immediately recognizes the letter combinations as specific words. Special distinction is added to certain letters that contain “ascenders”. These are letterforms such as “d”, “h” and “t”. They break above the regular upper level of letters (such as x) and make reading easier. They do this by showing distinction. The same holds true for “descenders”, which break below the bottom of regular letters (Spiekermann, 1993: 93).

adept typography

Figure 9. The shapes created by ascenders and descenders in Times New Roman

Many typefaces have been designed over time for special needs. The idea that special type performs special functions is virtually lost in communications today. For example, many typefaces were designed in the 1930s to 1940s to perform better when read in newspapers. Some of these typefaces are still in general use, such as Times New Roman, created for the London Times in 1931. Mergenthaler Monotype created a full set of typefaces for newspaper applications. These designs were introduced to solve reproduction challenges. Deemed the “Legibility Group”, several of these typefaces are in general use today (Spiekermann, 1993: 57).

Corona Excelsior

Figure 10. Two members of the family of typefaces called The Legibility Group

This paper's findings show that text can introduce channel noise into visual communication. The use of all caps, especially for continuous texts, white text on dark backgrounds, continuous text in sans serif text, or bodies of text aligned flush right can add noise (Wheildon, 1995).

CHANNEL NOISE WITHIN DATA GRAPHICS

The aim of good data graphics is to display data accurately and clearly (Wainer, 1984: 137). Data graphics may be designed for succinct communication or maligned by decorative or poorly conceived design. When data is cross-referenced and relational, it becomes more difficult to distinguish what is clear and what is not.

This section will overview several of Edward Tufte's theories of data graphics design in order to understand the attempts of visual designers to convey information clearly.

In the *Visual Display of Quantitative Information*, originally published in 1983, Edward Tufte discusses causes of noise in the design of data graphics. The following sections examine several of these ideas.

THE RATIO OF INFORMATION TO NON-INFORMATION

Tufte used "ink" as a metaphor for graphic markings – the use of black text, graphics or images on a white page (or screen). The ratio of superfluous imagery to data may be calculated with Tufte's simple formula (Tufte, 2001: 93).

$$\text{data ink ratio} = \frac{\text{data-ink}}{\text{total ink used to print the graphic}}$$

Figure 11. Tufte's data-ink ratio (Tufte, 2001: 93). (redrawn)

This represents the ratio of information to non-information in a visual message. Most graphics don't have a 1:1 ratio of data ink to graphic ink. Some extra ink is often used, such as a subtle grid, to give some context to the data (Tufte, 2001).

Tufte's data-ink formula equates to the formula for signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) used in information theory where $S/N = \text{signal power} / \text{noise power}$ (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2010)

$$\text{signal-to-noise ratio} = \frac{\text{signal power}}{\text{noise power}}$$

Figure 12: The standard formula for signal to noise ratio

The effect of too much non-information in a data graphic is that the non-information distracts the message receiver from clearly seeing the data. In regards to visual channel noise, the channel noise begins to compete with, or overwhelm the visual message, as seen in *figure 13*.

Figure 13. Non-information can overwhelm valuable information in data graphics. Retrieved November 8, 2010 from: <http://www.syllent.com/media.html>

Tufte's data-ink fraction, and signal-to-noise ratio, both act as simple formulae to calculate message fidelity in data graphics. This suggests that both the amount of non-information, and the form of the information presented (as seen in the typographic noise in section 2 of this paper) affect visual channel noise. Operator error and the uninformed decisions of the designer, compromise the information signal in visual communications.

OPTICAL EFFECTS

Optical art was an aesthetic and philosophical movement in art in the 1960s. Its Hungarian master, Victor Vasarely (see *figure 14*) developed a researched painting philosophy based on theories of perception and pre-existing painting techniques (Arnason, 1977: 673).

Optical effects crept from the world of art into visual communications through the technological tools used by designers to arrange statistical data, which, according to Tufte, was "a twentieth-century innovation" resulting in "unintentional optical art" (Tufte, 2001: 107-111).

The ability of the designer to create contrasting areas began with the use of transparent sheets of transferable graphics such as *Letratone*, available in the 1960s and was later adopted by computer software designers in programs such as Excel and Illustrator into the mid 1980s (Tufte, 2001: 111).

Figure 14. Optical Art painting (Vasarely, 1970s) Retrieved November 8, 2010 from: <http://www.mantiquesmodern.com/itemdetails.php?id=246288>

Figure 2. Serial Echocardiographic Assessments of the Severity of Regurgitation in the Pulmonary Atrioventricular Valve in 31 Patients. The numerical grades were assigned according to the severity of regurgitation, as follows: 0, none; 0.5, mild; 1.0 to 1.5, mild to moderate; and 3.0, severe.

Figure 15. Optical effects in a data graphic (Tufte, 2001: 109)

The challenge of using optical effects in statistical data graphics is that they create “moiré” patterns (Tufte, 2001: 108). These patterns cause vibrations and distortions in human perception, the appearance of edges and inversions in depth perception (Oster, 1968: 64), resulting in visual noise. The noise interferes with the communication of information within the graphic (figure 15).

Information printed from PDF files that were scanned from existing documents may display moiré effects as the scanner misrepresents the original dot structure of previously printed material. PDF writers also degrade graphic files when improperly formatted.

LAYOUTS: INTERACTIVITY, SPACE AND LAYERING OF MESSAGE ELEMENTS

Confusion and clutter are failures of design, not attributes of information (Tufte, 1990: 53)

Text, graphics, and images, which are placed together, interact. Their colour, intensity and relative size may interfere, creating noise, yet these attributes of visual information may also be fashioned in ways that improve the interactivity and meaning of complex visual messages (Tufte, 1990: 53).

INTERACTIVITY

Novels have many pages of full columns of text. Most graphic presentations do not. They possess images and words, graphics and narratives. Plain instructional texts have the potential for meaning, depending on their use (Swarts, 2004: 69), but interactive presentations of pictures and images further visualize and develop meaning.

Figure 16. Modified instructional text sample (Swarts, 2004: 84)

Swarts’ term for the common modification of plain texts is “grounding” (Swarts, 2004: 68). Grounding occurs when people using instructional texts as tools, need to temporarily restructure the information they are using. They resort to a process of improvised design. People modify instructional texts to become more valuable to their personal needs (see figure 16). Like cookbooks in which users convert kilograms into pounds, texts become tools when users adapt the way the texts structure and represent information for specific tasks (Swarts, 2004: 67).

The improvised modifications of instructional texts described by Swarts suggest a similarity to the process of visual designers – a tendency to mediate and restructure their own texts to offer better

communication. Annotations, highlights and pictures in margins are necessary to create meaningful information (Swarts, 2004: 82-83). Meaning becomes immediate and deep when various elements of information correlate. Yet, like the example in *figure 16*, correlated information may become busy. It may contain noise.

An omnipresent, yet subtle, design issue is involved: the various elements collected together... interact, creating non-informative patterns and texture simply through their combined presence (Tufte, 1990: 53).

Tufte's reference to non-informative patterns is a direct correlation to visual channel noise. Visual channel noise in layouts may be created by the visual patterns unintentionally created when juxtaposing images, text and graphics (Tufte, 1990).

SPACE

In tests performed by Lonsdale in 2006 and 2007, examination layouts were tested for legibility and comprehensibility issues to see if layout design could affect test scores of examination candidates (Lonsdale, 2007).

In a situation of time and performance pressure, the aim of the candidate is to avoid both wasting time and making errors (Lonsdale, 2007: 115).

Significant advantages were found with examination layouts designed to conform to comprehensibility guidelines. Lonsdale prepared 2 layouts of examination materials. The first set was designed conforming highly to comprehensibility guidelines and was spaciouly designed and easy to read. According to previous research, Lonsdale followed typesetting and layout formats similar, yet not identical to Wheildon's research findings. Typographic features included serif text, 10 to 11 point size with 11 to 14 point of line spacing. Paragraphs were set flush left with no hyphenation in a single column of text, between 60 and 70 characters wide (Lonsdale, 2007: 116). (*Wheildon would have preferred justified text*)

The second set was designed through researching IELTS (International English Language Testing System) examinations. Lonsdale examined several different versions of these tests and established the more frequently occurring typographic features, which were then used to construct an average IELTS

layout. This layout was considered against comprehensibility guidelines to be at a medium level (Lonsdale, 2007: 118).

The studies showed that participants could read the high-level material faster, with more ease, answering questions more accurately. Participants felt when answers were found easily and answered easily, their test results were better, and this was supported by the findings (Lonsdale, 2007: 133).

The participants' most consistent comments mentioned "space" as their preferred typographic feature. Space between lines of text, paragraphs and questions is necessary to distinguish the autonomy of areas of information the human eye tries to access (Lonsdale, 2007: 133). This research suggests that visual channel noise is created when a jammed layout confuses the eye.

LAYERING

Among the most powerful devices for reducing noise and enriching the content of displays is the technique of layering and separation (Tufte, 1990: 53).

The use of layering images and text in visual communications allows for the separation and distinction of visual element planes from each other. These separate planes can contain different streams of information simultaneously (Tufte, 1990). The following example shows how visually noisy information can be made distinct and understandable by separating information into layers of colour. This exploded view of a copier uses black and red colours to achieve a simultaneously informative design.

Figure 17: detail of diagram of photocopier parts using colour to layer visual information (Tufte, 1990: 54)

The opposite holds true when images are overlaid without enough contrast of colour, value or form.

Modern visual communicators may achieve this purposefully or accidentally. It is evident by the subtle nature of effective layering that layering requires a degree of skill. The following example is a poster for a student recruitment campaign. Layering has been used to confuse visual elements to achieve the designer's desired aesthetic.

Figure 18: Cranbrook University recruitment poster (McCoy, 1989)
Retrieved November 12, 2010 from:
<http://hubpages.com/hub/Design-History-Through-the-Ages>

In his book, *Meggs History of Graphic Design* (2006: 492), Meggs claims that the poster shown in Figure 20 “demonstrated a complexity of form and meaning”, yet this poster is also an example of how layering can fail. The idea that there is artistic merit in cryptic visual messages is elaborated in Meggs’ further description of the visual devices used by the designer. McCoy overlaid different levels of visual and verbal messages, requiring her audience to decipher them (Meggs, 2006: 492). This raises the question, if hard-to-understand messages are aesthetically pleasing, do the positive effects of the aesthetics outweigh the poster’s lack of immediate meaning? Will people want to decipher the information encoded by the designer? Ogilvy (1983), Wheildon (1995) and Tufte (2001) suggest, no.

Annotated and illustrated texts may offer immediate and deep meaning to readers, yet these layouts may

generate high levels of visual channel noise. Space within designed layouts must be managed to help the information to be distinct, yet interactive enough to have meaning. Layering must be managed effectively to separate streams of information, and to avoid superimposing information upon itself.

DISCUSSION

The existence of channel-noise in visual communication is evident. Typeface design and typesetting choices such as paragraph layout and text colour can elevate levels of visual noise within bodies of text. The amount of non-information within a graphic can compromise its key message, as can optical effects that compete with the data’s ability to be clearly distinguished. While these effects are mostly caused by the designer’s ability to properly encode messages, graphic decoys are deliberately created, and have poor message fidelity.

Visual layouts can provide deeper information than plain texts, but can display interference between various elements causing visual noise. The use of appropriate amounts of space in layouts may decrease visual noise, but jammed layouts increase it. Layering may be used to separate streams of information, but must be skillful, or the information streams can superimpose, creating visual confusion.

There is evidence of findings that relate to design issues from several disciplines, such as behavioural sciences, information theory, visual communications theory, typographic design, and education. Further work within a multidisciplinary approach, paralleling similar work from more mature disciplines may bear fruit for design theory. By bringing together existing research findings into a common body of knowledge, designers could be made more aware of the negative effects of increasing the levels of visual channel noise in the mediated messages they produce.

The use of existing terminology, such as “channel noise” could offer more conceptual clarity and more interdisciplinary functionality than less descriptive, currently used terms like “busy” may offer. The term “channel noise” may both enhance designers’ standards of design terminology and enlighten designers’ understanding of the behaviours of the

mediated messages they produce. Other terms such as “signal-to-noise ratio” may also offer more interdisciplinary functionality than custom terms like “data-ink ratio” (Tufte, 2001: 93). Today, both “channel noise” and “signal-to-noise ratio” are not in common use in the design lexicon.

CONCLUSION

The communications concepts of Shannon, Osgood and Schramm, Pettersson, Kneupper and Underwood, all inform a base understanding of the processes in visual communication. We developed a visual communications model based on these parallel models, focusing on the mediated messages of visual design. These mediated messages correspond to the “signal” section of models such as Shannon’s and Schramm’s (Shannon, 1948; Schramm, 1954). These model sections are referred to as the “channel”. Each model exhibited forms of message disruption that enter the system between the sender and receiver of a message. These disruptions are referred to as “noise” (Shannon, 1948; Shannon, Weaver, 1998; Kneupper, Underwood, 1976).

By analyzing the components of visual messages: text, data graphics and layouts including various visual elements, noise-generating features were found to exist in visual communications channels (Wheildon, 1995; Tufte, 2001; Lonsdale, 2007).

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FIGURES

Figures on pages 1,5 and 6 by David Craib, 2010.